

OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF PACS- A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Article History

Received on: 23-Mar 2026

Revised on: 29-Apr-2026

Accepted on: 28- May 2026

First Published: 05-Jun-2026

Cite this Article as

SK Hota & Shibani S (2026), "Operational Efficiency Of PACS- A Comparative Study", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 14, Issue1, 2026, pp 209- 219

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20559438>

ABSTRACT

Primary Agricultural Cooperative Society (PACS) dealing with mainly the agricultural credit plays a vital role in rural credit delivery and agricultural development in India. An attempt has been made in this study compares the financial performance of the PACSs (Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies) located in different blocks of irrigated and non-irrigated area in Bargarh district of Odisha state by applying the CAMEL framework. The Secondary sources of data from ten selected PACS (five irrigated and five non-irrigated) for the period 2019–20 to 2023–24 were considered for analyzing the capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, earnings quality, and liquidity. The findings indicate that the PACSs located in irrigated area perform significantly better in terms of capital strength, profitability, operational efficiency, and fund management than that of PACSs located in non-irrigated area. It is also observed that PACSs in non-irrigated area exhibit greater dependence on external borrowings and higher liquidity risks. However, no significant differences were observed in asset quality and short-term liquidity indicators. The study concludes that irrigation facilities positively influence the financial sustainability and overall performance of PACS. Strengthening irrigation access and managerial efficiency can enhance the resilience of PACS in non-irrigated areas.

Keywords: PACS, CAMEL Framework, Financial Performance, Irrigation, Operational Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian financial system has been dominated by commercial banks in almost all the sectors of the economy. However, cooperative institutions continue to play a vital role in extending financial services to rural areas through their extensive grassroots network. The cooperative credit movement in India dates back to the enactment of the Cooperative Credit Societies Act, 1904, and currently operates through a three-tier structure comprising State Cooperative Banks at the apex level, District Central Cooperative Banks at the district level, and Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS) at the village level. As the grassroots units

of the cooperative credit system, PACS serve as an important institutional mechanism for promoting financial inclusion, agricultural development, and rural economic growth. They provide short- and medium-term credit to farmers, particularly small and marginal cultivators, while also supporting agricultural activities through the supply of inputs, storage facilities, and marketing services (Johnson & Paul, 2024).

Despite their significant contribution to rural development, PACS face increasing operational and financial challenges in a rapidly evolving financial environment. Their long-term sustainability largely depends on maintaining sound financial performance and institutional efficiency. In this context, the CAMEL framework offers a comprehensive approach for evaluating the financial health of cooperative institutions through five dimensions: capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, earnings quality, and liquidity. Accordingly, the present study employs the CAMEL framework to assess the financial performance of PACS in Bargarh district of Odisha using selected financial ratios under each component, thereby examining their stability, efficiency, and overall financial soundness.

Objective

The objective of the study is to analyze the relative performance of PACSs located in irrigated and non-irrigated belt of the district under study in terms of certain specific financial parameters in order to deduce significant conclusion.

2. DATA BASE AND METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a descriptive research design based on secondary data obtained from the financial statements of selected Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies (PACSs) in Bargarh district, Odisha. The analysis covers a five-year period from 2019–20 to 2023–24. However, the mean value of the five year has been taken in this study For comparative assessment of ten PACS were selected, comprising five societies from irrigated areas and five from non-irrigated areas. Given the limited sample size and data availability, the study is exploratory in nature and does not aim to provide population-level estimates.

The financial performance of the selected PACS was evaluated using the CAMEL framework, which examines five dimensions: Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Management Efficiency, Earnings Quality, and Liquidity. Various financial ratios under the CAMEL framework were computed and compared to assess differences in financial stability,

operational efficiency, and overall performance between PACSs operating in irrigated and non-irrigated. The significance level of difference in various ratios between these two groups of PACSs operating in two different areas under study is statistically estimated by independent samples T-test.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The relative performance in the financial parameters considered for the study is analysed through various ratios to assess the financial health of PACSs operating in irrigated and non-irrigated area under study over time. The mean (average) of the ratios along with other descriptive statistics are depicted in Table-1 and the significance level of difference in various ratios between these two groups of PACSs operating in two different areas under study is statistically estimated by independent samples T-test as shown in Table-2. The theoretical fundamentals of various ratios estimated as depicted in Table-1 is as follows.

3.1 Capital Adequacy: Capital Adequacy Ratios are used to measure the financial strength and stability of PACS/banks. It includes (i) **Capital to Risk Asset Ratio (CRAR)** = Net worth / Risk weighted asset * 100, (ii) **Debt-Equity Ratio** - It measures the financial leverage of a firm by comparing its total debt to total shareholder's equity. Debt-Equity Ratio = Total Debt / Shareholder's Equity, (iii) **Advances or Loan to Assets Ratio** - It measures the proportion of total assets tied up in loans and advances and the higher value of this ratio indicates that the institution is utilizing its resources actively to generate income. Advances to Assets Ratio = Total Loans and Advances / Total Assets.

3.2 Asset Quality Ratio: It evaluates the financial soundness by examining the quality of its loan portfolio and investment. A sound asset quality base indicates effective credit appraisal, monitoring and recovery mechanisms. Whereas, poor asset quality reflects inadequate lending practices, weak supervision and higher credit risk. It includes (i) **NPA to Total Asset Ratio** - This ratio is estimated as Net NPA / Total Assets * 100, A higher ratio indicates greater risk and potential financial instability, (ii) **NPA to Net Advance Ratio** - The NPA to Net Advance Ratio indicates whether the provision is adequate to cover bad loans. A high value of this ratio indicates weak recovery, insufficient provisioning and higher financial vulnerability. It is estimated as Net NPA / Net Advance * 100, (iii) **Total Investment to Total Asset Ratio** - It measures the proportion of total assets that are deployed in the form of

investment. A balanced investment to asset ratio reflects diversification of funds, reducing dependence on a single type of asset. It helps to assess whether the institution is managing its asset portfolio efficiently. This ratio is estimated as $\text{Total Investments} / \text{Total Assets} * 100$.

3.3 Management Efficiency Ratios: It ensures the survival and growth of financial institutions. It evaluates how efficiently the management of a financial institution is utilizing its resources to generate returns and maintain stability. It reflects the institutions' quality of decision making, governance and operational efficiency. It includes (i) **Total Advance to Total Deposit Ratio-** This ratio measures the efficiency of management in converting the deposits available with the institution into high earning advances. It reflects how efficiently the institution is utilizing its deposit base to generate income through lending. It is estimated as $\text{Total Advance} / \text{Total Deposit} * 100$, (ii) **Business per employee-** It measures the productivity of human resources. A higher value of this ratio indicates efficient staff utilization and better managerial effectiveness. $\text{Business per Employee} = (\text{Total deposit} + \text{Total Advances}) / \text{Number of Employees}$, (iii) **Profit per employee-** It indicates how much profit each employee contributes to the institution. It reflects both operational efficiency and employee productivity. The higher the ratio, the higher is the efficiency of the management. $\text{Profit per Employee} = \text{Net Profit} / \text{Number of Employees}$.

3.4 Earning Quality Ratios: It assesses the sustainability, stability and sufficiency of income generated by a financial institution. It reflects how well the institution is using its resources to generate profit while managing risks. It includes (i) **Return on Asset (ROA)-** It reflects the overall operational efficiency of the institution. A higher value of ROA indicates better utilization of assets and strong profitability. $\text{Return on Asset ratio} = \text{Net Income} / \text{Total Assets} * 100$, (ii) **Return on Equity (ROE)-** It measures the profitability of financial institutions in relation to the shareholder's equity, which is crucial for the long-term viability and financial stability. A higher ROE indicates efficiency in generating profits. $\text{ROE} = \text{Net Income} / \text{Total Capital} * 100$, (iii) **Net Interest Margin Ratio or Spread to Total Asset Ratio-** This ratio measures the ability of a financial institution to generate income from its core business of lending and investing relative to its total assets. A higher spread ratio indicates better performance. In PACS, a healthy spread ratio is important for its sustainability. $\text{Spread to Total Asset Ratio} = \text{Net Interest Margin} / \text{Average Total Assets}$.

3.5 Liquidity Ratios: It measures the ability of a financial institution to meet its short-term financial obligations and provide funds to its members when needed. It reflects the institution's capacity to manage the cash flow and ensure the payoff of its liabilities. It

includes (i) **Cash & Bank Balance to Total Deposit Ratio**-It shows the liquidity available to meet immediate withdrawal demands of the depositors. Cash & Bank Balance to Total Deposit Ratio = (Cash in hand + Cash at Bank + other deposits) / Total Deposit, (ii) **Current Ratio**- It reflects the short-term financial health and operational efficiency of institutions like PACS. Current Ratio = Current Assets / Current Liabilities.

3.6 Comparative Analysis of Ratios

The Descriptive Statistics of Various Ratios for PACS operating in Irrigated and Non-Irrigated areas under study is depicted in Table-1. It provides the mean value of various ratios for PACs operated in irrigated and non-irrigated belt of the district under study which will be helpful for comparing their relative financial and operational efficiency. By examining the mean values of these groups, we can understand the operational and financial gaps created by irrigation facilities.

The comparison of various ratios estimated for the PACS operated in two different areas can be analysed broadly on the following grounds.

3.7 Capital Strength and Solvency

The PACSs operated in irrigated area demonstrate relatively stronger capital adequacy, with a mean CRAR of 39.61 as compared to 15.15 for PACSs operated in non-irrigated which indicates a greater capacity to absorb financial risks. Conversely, the higher Debt-Equity Ratio observed among PACSs operated in non-irrigated i.e,9.97 as compared to PACS of irrigated area i.e.7.47 reflects a greater dependence on external borrowings and a relatively weaker capital structure.

3.8 Asset Quality and Credit Exposure

The PACSs of Non-irrigated area exhibit a significantly higher Advance-to-Asset Ratio (0.73) than that of irrigated area (0.49), indicating greater credit exposure and a larger proportion of assets deployed as loans. The PACSs of irrigated area reported a marginally higher NPA-to-Asset Ratio (0.18 compared to 0.13) which may be attributed to their larger loan portfolios rather than weaker asset quality.

3.9 Operational Efficiency and Productivity

The PACSs of Irrigated area exhibit comparatively higher operational efficiency, generating an average business of ₹7.67 crore per employee as compared to ₹3.99 crore in non-irrigated area. Similarly, profit per employee is substantially higher in PACSs of irrigated area (₹40.86

lakh) than that of non-irrigated area (₹4.61 lakh), indicating more effective resource utilization and enhanced profitability.

3.10 Earning Capacity and Liquidity Management

The PACSs of Irrigated area demonstrate significantly higher profitability, with a mean Return on Assets (ROA) of 5.07% as compared to 1.36% for that of non-irrigated area, while the Return on Equity (ROE) is markedly higher at 62.49% for PACSs of irrigated area as compared to that of non-irrigated area i.e, 5.83%. In contrast, PACSs of non-irrigated exhibit a substantially higher Advances-to-Deposit Ratio i.e. 171.70 as compared to that of irrigated area i.e. 8.13, indicating greater liquidity risk arising from excessive credit expansion relative to deposit mobilization. They also maintain higher cash-to-deposit ratios i.e. 3.51 as compared to PACSs of irrigated area i.e. 0.31, reflecting less efficient utilization of available funds.

It can be inferred from the analysis of Table-1 that PACSs operating in irrigated area are found financially more stable than that of non-irrigated area. They possess stronger capitalization, higher earning capacity, and better managerial efficiency. On the other hand, PACSs operating in non-irrigated area are more vulnerable, showing a heavy reliance on external funds and poor liquidity management. These results suggest that irrigation infrastructure is a primary driver of institutional health for cooperatives in Bargarh district.

3.11 Independent Samples T-Test Results

Table-2 represents the Independent Samples T-Test Results which show the statistical significance of the differences found in the mean values of ratios depicted in Table-1 for the two groups of PACSs operating two different areas.

The independent samples t-test was conducted to determine if the differences in financial performance between PACSs operating in irrigated and non-irrigated areas are statistically significant. The analysis reveals that irrigation facilities have a profound impact on almost all key performance indicators.

3.12 Areas of Significant Difference

The results as shown in Table-2 indicate that PACSs of irrigated area significantly outweigh the performance of PACS of non-irrigated area in most of the financial and operational performance indicators ($p < 0.05$). PACSs of Irrigated area exhibit substantially stronger capital adequacy, with a mean Capital to Risk-weighted Assets Ratio (CRAR) of 39.61

compared to 15.15 for PACSs of non-irrigated area, while maintaining a lower Debt-Equity ratio of 7.47 as compared to 9.97 for the PACSs of non-irrigated area, reflecting reduced dependence on external borrowings and a healthier capital structure. In terms of operational efficiency, PACS of irrigated area generate considerably higher business volume and profit per employee, indicating superior resource utilization and greater scale of operations. Their profitability is also relatively higher, as evident from the Return on Assets (ROA) which is nearly four times greater and a Return on Equity (ROE) of 62.5%, as compared to only 5.83% for that of PACSs of non-irrigated area. Further, PACSs of irrigated area maintain significantly larger investment portfolios, suggesting better diversification and fund management practices. In contrast, PACSs of non-irrigated area display an exceptionally high Advance-to-Deposit ratio (171.7), indicating excessive credit extension relative to deposit mobilization and greater reliance on external funding sources. They also hold disproportionately high cash balances relative to deposits, reflecting inefficient liquidity management and the presence of idle funds. The Overall, the findings underscore the positive role of irrigation in enhancing the financial stability, profitability, operational efficiency, and sustainability of PACS

3.13 Areas with No Significant Difference

Two indicators, namely the NPA-to-Asset Ratio and Current Ratio, did not show statistically significant differences between PACSs of irrigated and non-irrigated area ($p > 0.05$). The similarity in NPA levels reveals ineffective loan recovery performance for both the groups with comparatively more in PACSs of irrigated areas even though the PACSs of irrigated area are handling larger loan portfolios. Likewise, the Current Ratio remained nearly identical for PACSs of irrigated (1.218) and non-irrigated (1.168) area, indicating similar short-term liquidity positions irrespective of irrigation facilities

4. FINDINGS

It is found from the analysis that irrigation facilities significantly enhance the financial performance and resilience of Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies (PACSs) in Bargarh district. PACS operating in irrigated areas exhibit stronger capital adequacy, reflected in a substantially higher mean Capital to Risk-Weighted Assets Ratio (CRAR) of 39.61, indicating greater financial stability and lower dependence on external borrowings. In contrast, PACSs located in non-irrigated areas demonstrate a higher debt-equity ratio, suggesting greater reliance on debt financing and increased financial vulnerability.

The profitability and operational efficiency found relatively higher for PACSs of irrigated area. These societies generate higher profits per employee and record a Return on Assets (ROA) nearly four times greater than that of PACSs operating in non-irrigated area, indicating more effective utilization of available resources. Moreover, a wider interest spread highlights their stronger financial intermediation capacity. The PACSs of Irrigated area also maintain a larger and more diversified investment portfolio, whereas PACSs of non-irrigated area exhibit a significantly higher advances-to-deposit ratio, exposing them to liquidity risks. The tendency of PACSs operating in non-irrigated area is to retain substantial idle cash balances which reflects inefficiencies in fund management.

However, no statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups with respect to the NPA-to-asset ratio and current ratio, indicating comparable loan recovery performance and short-term liquidity positions. Overall, the findings suggest that access to irrigation positively influences the financial sustainability, profitability, and capital strength of PACS. Therefore, targeted policy interventions and institutional support are essential for strengthening the long-term viability of PACS operating in non-irrigated regions.

5. CONCLUSION

The comparative assessment made between PACS of irrigated and non-irrigated using the CAMEL framework reveals a substantial performance gap influenced by differences in their operational environment. PACS located in irrigated areas exhibit stronger financial stability, profitability, operational efficiency, and capital adequacy, whereas PACS of non-irrigated area face challenges such as lower profitability, higher dependence on external funds, and weaker financial performance. The findings suggest that access to irrigation, coupled with efficient management and diversified business activities, plays a critical role in enhancing the financial health and long-term sustainability of PACS. Strengthening these factors in non-irrigated regions can improve their resilience, operational effectiveness, and overall financial viability.

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Table.1: Descriptive Statistics of Various Ratios for PACS of Irrigated and Non-Irrigated area (A Comparative Analysis)

	Ratios	Type (Area operation of PACS by irrigation status)	N (No. of PACS)	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Capital Adequacy	CRAR	Irrigated	25	39.6112	17.20015	3.44003
		Non-irrigated	25	15.1528	11.9666	2.39332
	Debt-Equity	Irrigated	25	7.4676	2.14712	0.42942
		Non-irrigated	25	9.9772	1.76334	0.35267
	Advance to Asset	Irrigated	25	0.4964	0.08703	0.01741
		Non-irrigated	25	0.73	0.06739	0.01348
Asset Quality Ratio	NPA to Asset	Irrigated	25	0.1889	0.10978	0.02196
		Non-irrigated	25	0.1346	0.10835	0.02167
	NPA to Advance	Irrigated	25	0.2864	0.1979	0.03958
		Non-irrigated	25	0.1712	0.13217	0.02643
	Investment to Asset	Irrigated	25	0.4576	0.13255	0.02651
		Non-irrigated	25	0.1286	0.05298	0.0106
Management Efficiency Ratio	Advance to Deposit	Irrigated	25	8.138	6.06062	1.21212
		Non-irrigated	25	171.7032	119.52482	23.90496
	Business Per Employee	Irrigated	25	76743935.02	71334969.28	14266993.85
		Non-irrigated	25	39928623.44	21623180.75	4324636.15
	Profit Per Employee	Irrigated	25	4086405.31	3072778.04	614555.61
		Non-irrigated	25	461032.82	2015036.48	403007.3
Earning Quality Ratio	ROA	Irrigated	25	5.0775	3.22537	0.64507
		Non-irrigated	25	1.3598	3.19325	0.63865
	ROE	Irrigated	25	62.4956	40.76354	8.15271
		Non-irrigated	25	5.8316	59.35623	11.87125
	Spread to Asset	Irrigated	25	0.0233	0.02739	0.00548
		Non-irrigated	25	0.0014	0.01672	0.00334
Liquidity Ratio	Cash to Deposit	Irrigated	25	0.3129	0.59211	0.11842
		Non-irrigated	25	3.5112	3.66633	0.73327
	Current Ratio	Irrigated	25	1.218	0.1565	0.0313
		Non-irrigated	25	1.1682	0.37921	0.07584

Table-2: Results of Independent Samples T-Test

Ratio	Levene's F	Levene's Sig.	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Result
CRAR	7.169	0.01	5.836	0	Significant
Debt Equity	1.859	0.179	-4.516	0	Significant
Advance to Asset	1.805	0.185	-10.611	0	Significant
NPA to Asset	0.524	0.473	1.76	0.085	Not Significant
NPA to Advance	2.68	0.108	2.42	0.019	Significant
Investment to Asset	10.213	0.002	11.523	0	Significant
Advance to Deposit	66.402	0	-6.834	0	Significant
Business Per Emp.	7.19	0.01	2.469	0.02	Significant
Profit Per Emp.	4.18	0.046	4.933	0	Significant
ROA	0.08	0.778	4.096	0	Significant
ROE	0.112	0.74	3.935	0	Significant
Spread to Asset	0.077	0.782	3.418	0.001	Significant
Cash to Deposit	16.54	0	-4.306	0	Significant
Current Ratio	0.3	0.586	0.606	0.547	Not Significant